

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

September 18, 2025
LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

Co-funded by
the European Union

LOGOS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

September, 2025

EDITORS

Valbona NATHANAILI
Logos University College

Elona KARAFILI
Polis University

Blerta DRENOFCI (CANI)
Logos University College

Konstantinos GIAKOUMIS
Logos University College

Dužanka BOŠKOVIĆ
University of Sarajevo

Arbana KADRIU
South East European University

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an initiative of LOGOS University College, supported by the consortium
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Address: Rr: “Dritan Hoxha”, Tiranë.

valbona.nathanaili@kulogos.edu.al

www.kulogos.edu.al

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VALBONA NATHANAILI

LOGOS University College

Dr. Nathanaili is currently a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania, with an experience of more than 35 years in the field of academia and publication. She is a Bachelor in physics and a doctoral degree holders in the science of pedagogy, both from University of Tirana. Major areas of research over the last few years are the politics and reforms in Albanian Education System, methodology of teaching science, university pedagogy, the future of schooling and Recognition and Accreditation of Prior Learning gained after flexible learning paths. She is analyst, writers and contributor for different periodic Albanian newspaper and television outlets. Nathanaili, in collaboration with different HEIs, has been initiator and supporter of STEM national campaigns, to encourage girls to pursue careers in science, technology, engineering and math fields and promote women in those fields. Dr. Nathanaili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects.

KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUIMIS

LOGOS University College

Konstantinos Giakoumis is Professor of History, Arts and Didactics at LOGOS University College, where he also leads the Faculty of Humanities and Linguistic Communication. He is a doctoral degree (Ph.D.) holder PhD from the University of Birmingham, serves on the international advisory board of Art Readings (Institute of Art Studies, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences) and reviews for the Serbian Academy of Sciences, the University of Crete, and international journals including *Speculum* (University of Chicago Press), the *Journal of Religious History* (Wiley), and *Politics, Religion & Ideology* (Taylor & Francis). He has also served as coordinator of a number of ERASMUS+ CBHE projects (Roaming, Homo Digitalis, DiLanEdu-WB). For a Marie Curie fellowship application in 2018 he received the European Commission's Seal of Excellence. A prolific scholar, his work appears in leading journals such as *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* (Cambridge), *Turkish Historical Review* (Brill), and the *International Journal of Cultural Policy* (Taylor & Francis). His most recent book examines the Codex of the Diocese/Metropolis of Dryinoupolis and Gjirokastra (1760–1858), published by LOGOS University College Press.

ELONA KARAFILI

POLIS University

Dr. Elona Karafili is an expert in the field of economic development. She is a lecturer and researcher at POLIS University, Tirana, Albania since 2007. She holds a PhD in Urban Planning from Ferrara University and Polis University. Elona currently holds the position of the Deputy Rector of POLIS University. Her main topics of interest and expertise

include regional economic development and territorial competitiveness, which she has explored through a number of projects that focus on place-based innovation. Dr. Karafili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects. She is enthusiastic to strengthen the innovation ecosystem in Albania through fostering co-creative processes, academia–business collaboration and knowledge transfer, startup support and commercialization of research.

DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ

University of Sarajevo

Vice Rector for Quality at the University of Sarajevo and a Professor at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. Her research interests and teaching are focused on software engineering in biomedical and cognitive domains. She is highly motivated to learn about problem domains and committed to achieving a high level of user experience. In addition to teaching and research, she is engaged in various activities aimed at improving education in Bosnia and Herzegovina, especially through promoting student-centered and outcome-based learning and using software as educational content.

BLERTA DRENOFCI (CANI)

LOGOS University College

Dr. Drenofci has devoted her efforts for last 20 years at the Albanian Disability Rights Foundation, to the activities in advocacy and lobbying for disability related policy and legislation adoption and implementation and offering of supportive services for people in need throughout the country. She is an expert in the area of social policies and collaborator in the formulation of policy framework for people with disabilities in Albania. She has directed ADRF contribution in several important legal initiatives. ADRF is acknowledged as the pioneer and leader of human rights-based approach to disability and it is one in the few organizations that offer models of supportive services like mobility means, supported employment, free legal aid for people in need in Albania. Blerta has an PhD in Social Sciences and has an academic background, being a teacher of University of Tirana since 2013. She has been the leader and the author of a lot of studies in the field of social policies in and outside the country. She has been involved as a consultant in the research and policy development by several international agencies. During the years 2014-2022, she has been involved in the development of the new reform for the assessment of disability in Albania, based on international standards.

ARBANA KADRIU

South East European University

Arbana Kadriu is a Full Professor of Computer Science at the Faculty of Contemporary Sciences and Technologies, South East European University (SEEU) in Tetovo, North Macedonia. She earned her PhD in Computer Science from Ss. Cyril and Methodius

University, Skopje (2008), specializing in natural language processing and information retrieval. Her research spans AI and machine learning, software engineering, web information retrieval, social network analysis, and e-learning, with a growing focus on speech technologies for low-resource languages. Prof. Kadriu teaches across undergraduate, master's, and doctoral programs, organized into three clusters: Data & Intelligence, Software & the Web, and Research & Methods. She has supervised numerous master's and PhD theses in areas such as data mining–driven decision support, Albanian speech recognition, authorship analysis, and automatic music generation. Prof. Kadriu has authored 70+ publications across journals and international conferences (IEEE, Springer, PLOS ONE, and others) and contributes to international projects, including Erasmus+ initiatives on digital humanities and quality assurance, as well as COST actions on language technology and language learning.

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DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

SEPTEMBER 18, 2025

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in collaboration with:

- University of Patras
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SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Trends, Challenges and Perspectives

Logos University College, Tirana, Albania

Thursday, September 18, 2025

9.00-9.30	Registration
9.30-10.00	Open remarks
	Ilia Ninka, rector, LOGOS University College
	Gertiola Cepani, Director of Labour Market Services at 'National Employment and Skills Agency'
	Konstantinos Giakoumis, HOMO DIGITALIS Project Coordinator

TOPIC

AUTHOR(S)

OPPONENT

FIRST CONFERENCE TRACK			
Digital Competences in Higher Education and the Labour Market			
10.00-10.20	1. The Impact of Digital Transformation on Human Resource Management. Case Study: Albanian Universities During the Pandemic Period	Emira Spahaj, Edisela Mena, Malvina Hysa, Blerta Avdia	Elona Karafli
10.20-10.40	2. Barriers and Opportunities in Albanian Higher Education for Students with Disabilities: A Mixed-Methods Analysis	Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Valbona Nathaniaili	Merima Muslić
10.40-11.00	3. The Digital Employment Gap in Albania: Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education	Gertjana Hasalla	Arberore Bicaj
SECOND CONFERENCE TRACK			
Institutional Strategies and Policy Development			
11.00-11.20	4. Integrated Technical Assessment and Restoration Strategy for the "Topulli" House: Restoration Strategies, Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies	Nikolla Vesho, Panagiotis Kyriatsis, Ajla Gjoka, Lumturi Haska, Sara Ciba, Migena Gjoni, Ardis Duka, Romir Mazari	Konstantinos Giakoumis
11.20-11.40	5. The Role of MOOCs and Open Educational Resources in Higher Education: Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science	Dorina Minxuri	Valbona Nathaniaili

11.40 -12.00	6. Language Technologies and Digital Humanities for Low-Resource Languages and Communities	Arbana Kadriu, Lejla Abazi-Bexheti	Blerta Drenofci (Çani)
12.00-12.20	Coffee break		
12.20-12.40	7. The Cognitive–Digital Turn in Higher Education. <i>A Longitudinal Analysis of AI Engagement in an Architectural Design Studio</i>	Fulvio Papadhopulli, Megi Tafaj	Nikolaos Avouris
12.40-13.00	8. Defining a Strategic Action Plan for AI in Higher Education	Nikolaos Avouris	Valbona Nathaniai
13.00-13.20	9. Institutional Policies and Strategic Directions for Advancing Digital Competencies in Higher Education	Hajdin Berisha, Agron Hajdari, Bekim Samadraxha	Flora Krasniqi
THIRD CONFERENCE TRACK			
The intended and attained curriculum			
13.20-13.40	10. Digital Competencies in Social Sciences – A Pilot Study. <i>From Design to Practice: Teaching Approaches in the HOMO DIGITALIS Project</i>	Valbona Nathanaïli, Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Konstantinos Giakoumis, Dušanka Bošković, Arbana Kadriu, Anisa Duka	Bujar Gallopeni
13.40-14.00	11. Enhancing Learning through Multimedia Cultural Heritage Applications: Managing Cognitive Load	Merima Muslić, Dušanka Bošković, Vensada Okanović, Selma Rizvić	Blerta Avdia
14.00-14.20	12. Integrating Digital Competencies into Higher Education Curricula. <i>A Case Study from LOGOS University College within the Homo Digitalis Project</i>	Juna Muça, Anxhela Laska, Elpiniqi Merkuri, Edvaldo Begotaraj	Emira Spahaj
14.20-15.40	Lunch		
20.00-22.00	Social Dinner and Awarding of Certificates of Participation and Presentation of Papers		

**PART ONE:
DIGITAL COMPETENCES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION
AND THE LABOUR MARKET**

THE ROLE OF MOOCS AND OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science

Dorina MINXURI

LOGOS University College
dorina.minxuri@kulogos.edu.al

Abstract

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) and Open Educational Resources (OER) have emerged as transformative tools in higher education. For fields like medicine and laboratory sciences, where constant innovation and updated protocols are essential, MOOCs and OERs represent an invaluable complement to traditional teaching. These resources enhance accessibility, flexibility, and student engagement, while bridging gaps between theory and clinical practice. This paper explores the role of MOOCs and OERs in higher education, with a particular focus on teaching laboratory sciences, and examines how these resources can support student-centered learning. A comparative analysis is provided between traditional lecture-based instruction and student-centered approaches supported by OER and MOOCs. Findings suggest that OER-supported teaching improves knowledge retention, practical skills, and clinical reasoning.

Keywords: Laboratory science, student-centered learning, MOOC, OER

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

DORINA MINXURI

Dorina Minxuri is a full-time lecturer at the Department of Health Sciences and Social Welfare, Faculty of Applied Sciences, at LOGOS University College, where she has been teaching since 2015. She earned her Master of Science degree in General Medicine at the University of Medicine in Tirana in 2010, and later pursued a four-year postgraduate specialization in Endocrinology and Diabetology (2011–2015). During this period, she also taught as a part-time lecturer at both the Faculty of Medicine in Tirana (Physiology) and Albanian University. In 2019, she began her doctoral studies at the Catholic University “Our Lady of Good Counsel”, focusing her research on thyroid gland pathologies, a field in which she continues to develop her expertise. Since 2017, she has also been practicing as an endocrinologist in a private outpatient service, where she is dedicated to the follow-up and treatment of individuals with endocrine disorders. Dr. Minxuri is the author and co-author of several scientific articles in the field of medicine and has presented her work at numerous national and international congresses and workshops in medicine and endocrinology. She is an active member of several professional organizations, including the Endocrine Society (ENDO Society), the International Society of Endocrinology (ISE), and the Healthcare & Biological Sciences Research Association (HBSRA).

INTRODUCTION

MOOCs are large-scale online courses open to learners worldwide, often offered free of charge or at low cost by universities and educational platforms (Yuan & Powell, 2013). OERs, on the other hand, are freely available teaching and learning resources such as textbooks, case studies, or videos that can be adapted and reused (Hilton, 2016). Together, MOOCs and OERs have emerged as vital innovations, enabling instructors to integrate updated content, case-based learning, and multimedia into teaching (Wiley *et al.*, 2014, Bonk *et al.*, 2018).

Applications in Medicine and Laboratory Science

Higher education, particularly in medical and laboratory sciences, faces the challenge of preparing students not only with theoretical knowledge but also with practical competencies and decision-making skills applicable to real-world clinical environments. Traditional teaching methods, often centered on didactic lectures, are increasingly considered insufficient for preparing students to navigate modern health care challenges (Laurillard, 2012). For pathophysiology and laboratory sciences, OER provide access to up-to-date diagnostic protocols, visual demonstrations of testing procedures, and interactive cases that mirror patient scenarios. MOOCs allow for flexible and scalable teaching, while offering certification in specialized laboratory competencies such as hematology, immunology, microbiology, and laboratory automation. By integrating *clinical case studies* from open resources, students are exposed to real-world patient problems and learn how to link theory to practice. *Demonstrative videos* - often simple, visual, and engaging - help explain complex mechanisms such as hormonal feedback loops or the interpretation of diagnostic results. Moreover, the inclusion of *updated laboratory testing protocols and technological guidelines* ensures that students remain current with professional standards.

MOOCs allow for flexible and scalable teaching and provide opportunities for quick and attractive learning outside of the classroom, while offering certification in specialized laboratory competencies such as hematology, immunology, microbiology, and laboratory automation. For instance, recommending short, free courses on platforms like Coursera, edX, or FutureLearn can enhance students' understanding of these concepts and not only reinforce knowledge but also cultivate lifelong learning skills (Hew & Cheung, 2014).

Student-Centered Learning and Critical Thinking

Traditional didactic teaching often leaves little space for students to actively engage, analyze, and make decisions. MOOCs and OERs play a critical role in this pedagogy by shifting responsibility for learning toward students. Instead of passively receiving information, students engage with case materials, interpret data, and make diagnostic decisions. This active learning model mirrors clinical practice, where health professionals must analyze patient data, consider alternatives, and act on evidence.

By using MOOCs and OERs, students can explore different pathways of knowledge at their own pace, revisiting difficult concepts as needed. This not only improves

comprehension but also fosters independent problem-solving and critical reasoning skills (Liu *et al.*, 2016). Ultimately, student-centered use of MOOCs and OERs helps prepare learners for the realities of laboratory medicine, where uncertainty and decision-making are everyday challenges.

Accredited MOOCs for Laboratory Competencies

One of the most promising applications of MOOCs in laboratory sciences is the creation of *accredited, institution-based online courses* for specific competencies. Universities can develop short, targeted MOOCs designed to certify laboratory skills, thus bridging the gap between theoretical teaching and workplace readiness. (Open WHO 2023) Examples include:

- *Hematological Testing*: peripheral smear interpretation, use of automated analyzers, and hematology case analysis.
- *Advanced Immunology Techniques*: ELISA interpretation, flow cytometry, and immunofluorescence microscopy.
- *Microbiology in Practice*: culture methods, antibiotic susceptibility testing, and biosafety protocols.
- *Laboratory Automation*: operation of automated analyzers, data integration, and quality control.

Such micro-MOOCs, if accredited and tied to continuing education credits, could grant students official certificates of competence, thereby improving employability and aligning education with labor market demands (Jansen & Konings, 2017). For medical schools, this innovation positions the institution at the forefront of professional training in laboratory sciences.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this study was to compare the effectiveness of traditional teaching methods with the integration of Open Educational Resources (OER) and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) in the field of clinical laboratory education. The study seeks to determine whether OER and MOOCs can enhance students' learning outcomes, engagement, and ability to apply knowledge in clinical contexts when compared to traditional lecture-based instruction. Importantly, the student cohort involved had already experienced an intensive shift toward online education during the COVID-19 pandemic. This prior adaptation to virtual classrooms, digital platforms, and self-directed learning created a level of familiarity that facilitated the continued use of MOOCs and OER. As a result, implementing these methods was not perceived as a disruptive change but rather as a natural extension of the students' learning environment.

More specifically, the study aimed to:

- Evaluate differences in student performance and competency acquisition between those enrolled in traditional classroom-based teaching and those using MOOCs and OER materials (e.g., videos, clinical case resources, updated laboratory testing protocols).

- Assess students' preferences and satisfaction with MOOCs and OER as supplementary or primary tools for laboratory education, with a focus on courses such as immunological testing, hematology, microbiology, and laboratory automation.
- Explore the advantages and limitations of MOOCs and OER in preparing laboratory students for real-world professional settings, emphasizing decision-making, analytical skills, and patient-centered practice.

By comparing these two approaches, the study intended to provide evidence on whether MOOCs and OER can complement or partially replace traditional methods in higher education for laboratory sciences, ultimately helping institutions design more flexible, accessible, and practice-oriented curricula.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted over two consecutive academic years 2023-2024 and 2024-2025 in the medical laboratory students. Students were organized into two Groups:

- Group A (n = 48): Students enrolled in the second and third academic years (2023-2024 period) received teaching exclusively through traditional, in-person laboratory sessions and lectures.
- Cohort B (n = 45): Students enrolled in the second and third academic years (2024-2025 period) received teaching that integrated Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) and Open Educational Resources (OERs), besides the traditional teaching. These materials were delivered primarily through the Microsoft Teams platform, which had already been adopted during the COVID-19 pandemic for online lectures, communication, and sharing of protocols. Using existing online platforms ensured students were familiar with digital tools, so no additional training was needed.

Interventions

During the OER/MOOC phase Microsoft Teams was used primarily to share online materials. Demonstrative videos, interactive cases, and updated protocols were made accessible asynchronously. Up to 20% of lecture contact hours - specifically those covering laboratory technique protocols (e.g., ELISA/CLIA principles, flow cytometry basics, PCR, RIA) - were delivered via MOOCs/OER and not re-lectured in class. An online forum was available for clarification. Completion of final tests and demonstration of laboratory skills (based on existing curricula) was mandatory and contributed to practical evaluation.

Measurement instruments:

- *Theoretical knowledge:* multiple-choice questions (MCQs) based on the standard curriculum and prior exams.
- *Practical competencies:* laboratory skill assessment using standardized procedures derived from validated laboratory protocols.

- *Student satisfaction and motivation*: assessed via structured questionnaires focusing on ease of use, accessibility, and perceived effectiveness of online platforms.
- *Time spent for teaching and learning* evaluated in both phases.

The online topics covered *exactly* the same learning outcomes the lecture would have; only the *mode* changes. While the examinations and competency checklists were aligned with existing curricula and laboratory protocols (thus reflecting validated standards of the program), the satisfaction questionnaire was developed for this study and was not piloted beforehand. However, its content drew from prior student experiences with Microsoft Teams during the COVID-19 pandemic, providing contextual grounding.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study involved undergraduate medical laboratory students as part of standard curriculum activities. Participation in the surveys and online modules (MOOCs and OER) was voluntary, and students were informed about the objectives and use of data. Ethical considerations were addressed by discussing the materials in class and obtaining students' verbal consent; no personal data were collected, and participation did not affect academic evaluation. During the OER/MOOC phase, Microsoft Teams was used primarily as a platform to share videos, laboratory protocols, and open educational materials, rather than for real-time instruction. This approach minimized any disruption to standard teaching while allowing students to access materials asynchronously. Given that the study involved routine educational activities and non-invasive assessments, ethical risks were minimal. This design was chosen for reasons of practicality and feasibility, as it allowed integration of digital resources within the real teaching environment without disrupting the curriculum.

RESULTS

This study compared two cohorts of undergraduate students in clinical laboratory sciences: Group A (n = 48), who received traditional teaching (lectures with PowerPoint, textbook study, and in-class laboratory demonstrations), and Group B (n = 45), who received instruction through MOOCs and OER-based learning modules integrated in traditional curriculum. Importantly, students in Group B were already adapted to online learning methods during the COVID-19 pandemic, which facilitated the implementation of this teaching model.

Knowledge Improvement

- Group A (traditional): mean improvement in test scores = 18%
- Group B (MOOCs + OER): mean improvement = 32%
- The difference between groups was statistically significant (t-test, $p < 0.01$).

Applied Competencies

- Group B performed significantly better in case-based clinical reasoning questions (mean score difference: +14%, $p < 0.05$).
- Group B also showed higher accuracy in hematological tests and immunological assays, attributed to prior exposure to demonstrative videos and structured OER protocols.

Hands-On Practice

- Group A benefited from real-time improvisation and spontaneous problem-solving during laboratory practice, which was limited in Group B due to the online format.

Engagement and Motivation (Survey Results)

- 85% of Group B students reported feeling more prepared for real-world clinical practice compared to 55% of Group A.
- Group B valued the comprehensive, easily accessible content, with the ability to revisit modules at their own pace without extending teacher contact hours.
- Teaching/learning time was shorter in Group B compared to Group A, suggesting higher efficiency.

Challenges with MOOCs and OER

- 32% of Group B students reported difficulties maintaining focus and consistency without the structured schedule of in-person classes.
- Lack of immediate interaction with instructors was frequently cited, as students could not ask spontaneous questions or receive real-time clarification.
- Extended screen time was perceived as tiring by several Group B students, in contrast to the more interactive classroom and laboratory sessions in Group A.

Table 1. Summary of Comparison between Traditional Teaching and MOOCs+OER

Aspect	Traditional Lecture	MOOCs + OER
Knowledge retention	Moderate	High
Clinical reasoning	Limited	Strong
Practical skills	Average	Above average
Engagement	Passive	Active, student-centered
Certification opportunities	None	Available (MOOC certificates)
Efficiency of information Delivery	Medium	High
Real-time communication	High	None
Emotional engagement	Low	High
Hands-on improvisation	High	None
Screen fatigue	High	Limited

DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

The findings of this study demonstrate that the use of MOOCs and OER-based instruction led to significantly greater learning gains compared to only traditional teaching methods in undergraduate clinical laboratory sciences. Students in Group B (MOOCs + OER) achieved a 32% mean improvement in test scores, nearly 1.8-fold higher than the 18% mean improvement observed in Group A (traditional teaching). This difference was statistically significant (t-test, $p < 0.01$), indicating that OER-based learning contributed to more effective knowledge acquisition.

In addition to theoretical knowledge, Group B showed superior performance in applied competencies. Specifically, case-based clinical reasoning scores were on average 14% higher than those of Group A ($p < 0.05$). These results suggest that structured online modules, enriched with demonstrative videos and standardized protocols, facilitated deeper understanding and practical readiness.

However, several limitations must be acknowledged:

- First, the study design compared two consecutive student cohorts. This introduces a potential cohort effect bias, as differences in performance and satisfaction may not be attributable solely to the teaching method but also to natural variations between groups. Randomized controlled trials or matched cohort designs would provide stronger evidence, but in this context, randomization was not feasible. The chosen design was primarily driven by practicality and access within the educational setting.
- Second, while the knowledge and competency assessments were based on existing exams aligned with the curriculum, and the checklists followed established laboratory protocols (supporting content validity), the student satisfaction questionnaire was not piloted prior to use. Nonetheless, its feasibility was supported by the fact that students had already become accustomed to interacting with online platforms during the COVID-19 pandemic, which served as an indirect pre-testing of their ability to engage with such instruments.
- Third, the COVID-19 context itself may have influenced results. Students in the experimental group had prior exposure to online learning platforms (e.g., Microsoft Teams), which were widely used during the pandemic for lectures, communication, and dissemination of educational materials. This prior adaptation likely reduced barriers to the implementation of MOOCs and OERs. While this may represent a bias favoring the intervention group, it also reflects a realistic teaching context, as online learning platforms remain part of routine academic practice post-pandemic.
- Finally, the sample size was modest (Group A: 48, Group B: 45), and findings may not be generalizable to other institutions or disciplines.

Despite these limitations, the study highlights the feasibility and educational value of integrating MOOCs and OERs into medical education, particularly in contexts where digital platforms are already embedded in teaching practices.

The findings support global evidence that MOOCs and OER enhance knowledge

acquisition, practical skills, and self-directed learning (Hew & Cheung, 2014; Hollands & Tirthali, 2015).. Traditional lectures, while useful for foundational theory, fail to fully engage students or connect knowledge to clinical practice (Bonk *et al.*, 2018). By contrast, OER-supported instruction encourages self-directed learning, critical thinking, and adaptability.

In laboratory sciences, access to free online courses allows students to rehearse protocols before practice, reducing errors and building confidence. The introduction of accredited MOOCs for specific laboratory skills represents a significant opportunity. For example, courses in hematological testing, advanced immunology techniques, microbiology in practice, and laboratory automation can both enrich the curriculum and provide students with career-relevant certifications (Yuan & Powell, 2013).

A major advantage of OER is flexibility: students can review updated protocols for immunoassays, molecular diagnostics, and automation systems at their own pace. Furthermore, institutions can offer certificate-based MOOCs in hematological testing, advanced immunology, microbiology practice, or lab automation, enhancing employability and lifelong learning.

Furthermore, teaching faculty can benefit from MOOCs designed for educators, focusing on student-centered learning, competency-based approaches, and case-based teaching strategies. These help align higher education with real-world health care demands, ensuring students are not only knowledgeable but also capable of decision-making in patient-centered contexts.

However, challenges remain. MOOCs often lack personal interaction, spontaneity, and the “emotional dimension” of classroom learning (Veletsianos & Shepherdson, 2016). While students generally appreciated the accessibility, flexibility, and clarity of OER and MOOCs, several drawbacks were also reported. Unlike traditional teaching, MOOCs and OER lack immediate interaction with instructors, making it difficult for students to ask spontaneous questions or receive instant clarification. Students missed the dynamics of face-to-face classes such as improvisation, humor, and motivating classroom interactions which often make learning more memorable. Completion of MOOCs requires a high level of self-discipline. Some students reported difficulties in maintaining focus and consistency without the structured schedule of in-person classes. While video demonstrations and virtual labs provided good visualization, they could not fully replicate the tactile and improvisational aspects of working in a real laboratory setting. Extended screen time for online learning was perceived as tiring by some students, especially compared with more interactive classroom and laboratory sessions.

CONCLUSIONS

MOOCs and OER are powerful tools in higher education, particularly in the field of clinical laboratory sciences where rapid advances in technology and diagnostic protocols demand updated knowledge and flexible learning models. Unlike traditional lectures, which rely on textbooks, PowerPoint presentations, and in-class demonstrations, MOOCs and OER provide students with highly concentrated, visually comprehensive content that can be revisited multiple times. This not only accelerates the learning process but also empowers

students to take greater responsibility for their own progress. (Rodriguez, C. O. 2012) (Daniel, J. 2012). Faculties of Education and Centers for Teaching and Learning play a central role in designing syllabi for MOOCs, since their mission is to foster inclusive, research-informed teaching practices that place student learning at the core (Nathanaili, 2024).

When integrated with traditional methods, MOOCs and OER create a blended approach that combines the efficiency of digital delivery with the depth of classroom-based interactions. In clinical laboratory training, this integration can help students acquire both the technical competencies (such as hematology, immunology, biochemistry protocols, microbiology practice, and automation systems) and the clinical reasoning skills needed for professional practice. In addition, institutions that recognize and accredit specific MOOCs with certificates - such as those focused on hematological tests, advanced immunology techniques, or laboratory automation - strengthen the bridge between open learning and professional recognition, making these tools more attractive for career development. (Conole, G. 2013; Downes, S. 2012).

Nevertheless, challenges remain. Students often report that MOOCs require higher self-motivation and discipline, as the absence of real-time communication, emotional interaction, and spontaneous improvisation can make the learning process feel less engaging than traditional classroom settings. (Lane, A. 2009). Elements such as humor, informal discussions, or the supportive presence of peers and instructors are often lost in online learning environments. These limitations, however, can be mitigated through blended learning models that combine the flexibility of MOOCs with mentorship, scheduled discussions, and interactive feedback sessions.

Looking forward, the most effective strategy for higher education institutions—especially in clinical laboratory sciences—will be to continue developing specialized MOOCs and OER modules that not only provide theoretical foundations but also simulate laboratory practice through virtual labs, case studies, and problem-solving tasks. (Sangrà *et al.*, 2013). By accrediting these modules and aligning them with professional competencies, universities can ensure that students graduate not only with knowledge but also with recognized skills directly applicable to the workforce. In this way, MOOCs and OER can evolve from supplementary tools into integral components of a modern, student-centered, and professionally relevant education system. (Siemens G.,2013)

Based on these observations, several recommendations emerge:

- Incorporate MOOCs and OERs into Core Teaching: Faculty should actively adopt case studies, open videos, and digital resources to enrich pathophysiology and lab science curricula.
- Encourage Lifelong Learning: By recommending short, free MOOCs, students gain tools for independent and continuous professional development.
- Promote Student-Centered Learning: Courses should be redesigned to use MOOCs and OERs as catalysts for decision-making, data analysis, and problem-solving.
- Develop Faculty Training: Institutions should train educators in leveraging digital resources for student-centered pedagogy.

- Create Accredited Micro-MOOCs: Universities should develop certified online courses for specific laboratory competencies, improving employability and linking education with real-world practice.

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Digital transformation is no longer a future aspiration. It is a current imperative.

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... with vision, with cooperation, and with determination, we can ensure that AI serves not just technology, but learning. Not just efficiency, but wisdom.

PROF. NIKOLAOS AVOURIS

Altogether, the case-studies in this volume trace a roadmap for higher education in the Western Balkans that amalgamates tradition and innovation, strives to pursue equitable access to digital opportunities, and positions regional universities as active contributors to Europe's wider digital transformation.

PROF. KONSTANTINOS GLAKOUMIS

info@kulogos.edu.al

